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Correlation and path coefficient studies of growth characters on glucomannan content of eddoe taro (*Colocasia esculenta* var *antiquorum*)

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Abstract. Glucomannan is classified as a non-starch polysaccharide and has positively affected health and beauty. The breeding program to create new varieties of taro with high glucomannan content is challenging and requires comprehensive studies to produce high-quality food. This study investigated the characters correlation and direct and indirect responses to glucomannan production in the tuber. The experiment was conducted in three locations with 14 genotypes of Eddoe taro using a full-block design with two replications. Ten characters were evaluated for their correlation to glucomannan, which was accomplished using path analysis for each location experiment and followed by model selection using the backward elimination method. The character of the cormel number always has a positive correlation with the glucomannan variable, either directly or indirectly, with a high value of the path coefficient. On the contrary, the difference between the correlation value and path coefficient for determining the selection criteria was unfulfilled because it was > 0.05 , and the residual effect was > 0.61 , indicating that this model insufficient to explain more than 60% of the influence of anything other than the standardized independent. According to the study's results, this character doesn't meet the requirements for selection criteria.

Keywords: cormels, functional food, non-starch polysaccharide, taro breeding, tuber

1. Introduction

Taro (*Colocasia esculenta* (L.) Schoot) is one of the world's staple foods, particularly in Africa, Asia, and Oceania. Tuber is part of the plant that is mostly consumed as a source of carbohydrates, and other parts, such as the petiole and leaves, are used as vegetables. Taro tubers provide a variety of nutrients that the body needs, including carbohydrates, protein, vitamins A and C, calcium, phosphorus, and potassium. Complex carbohydrates in the tuber consist of starch and non-starch polysaccharides [1].

Researchers are paying more attention to non-starch polysaccharides due to their benefits and potential for health improvement [2–4]. Glucomannan is a non-starch polysaccharide that is widely utilized in the development of functional foods, both for health and aesthetics. This substance is applied topically to treat acne-prone skin, prevent skin infections, promote collagen production, and control blood sugar levels [5, 6]. Glucomannan is a water-soluble non-starch polysaccharide stored in tuber organs which is also found in taro tubers [7, 8]. In Indonesia, plant source of glucomannan was edible species of Araceae family. The highest content of glucomannan was found in the tuber of *Amorphophallus muelleri* Bl. (Porang: 9.92% ww) and followed by *Amorphophallus paeoniifolius* (Suweg: 3.2% ww), *Colocasia esculenta* (L.) Schott. (Bentul: 2.4% ww), *Alocasia macrorrhiza* (L.) Schott. (Sente: 1.3% ww) and the lowest was *Xanthosoma* sp. (Endro/Mbote: 0.64% ww) [9].

High-glucomannan taro can be developed as a functional food. Functional food is any natural or processed food that contains known or unknown biologically-active compounds that, in defined, effective, non-toxic amounts, provide a clinically proven and documented health benefit for the prevention, management, or treatment of chronic disease [10, 11]. Taro tuber's glucomannan has not been widely studied, especially for quality product improvement and value-added enhancement. Taro breeding activities in Indonesia are limited compared to other crops, even though Indonesia has a hugely diverse taro germplasm [12]. Thus, there is a great opportunity to obtain taro genotypes with high-glucomannan content through selection. Correlation and path analysis between plant growth and yield characteristics can be used for superior plant selection. The study aimed to investigate the characters correlation and direct and indirect responses to glucomannan production in the Eddoe taro tuber.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study sites and plant materials

The research was conducted in three experimental fields. The first location was sub-district Setu of South Tangerang District, Banten Province (6°21'26.5"S 106°39'56.2"E). The second and third fields were in the West Java Province: Sub-district Cimanggu - Bogor District (6°34'29.3"S 106°47'09.5"E) and Sub-district Cijambe, Subang District (6°39'42.4"S 107°44'53.6"E). The characteristics of each field are presented in the table 1. The plant material was 14 genotypes of Eddoe taro from some provinces in Indonesia listed in the table 2.

Table 1. The experiment field characteristics

Characteristics	Setu	Cimanggu	Cijambe
Soil type	clay	silty clay-type soil	clay
C/N ratio	13	13	10
pH	6.2	5	4.5
Rainfall*	820 mm	1400 mm	493 mm
Humidity*	76%	82%	73%

*Source of data: climate station nearest from experiment field location

2.2. Experimental design and data collecting

The experiment was designed as a randomized block design consisting of 14 Indonesian taro accessions with two replications. Ten plant growth characters were measured 14 weeks after planting when the maximum vegetative growth was obtained. i.e., leaf length, petiole length, sheath length, total petiole length, plant height, cormus length, diameter of cormus, cormus weight, and cormels number. Taro tubers were harvested five months after planting, peeled, cleaned, sliced, dried at 80°C for 20 hours continuously, and ground into 80 mesh of flour [8]. The mixtures of cormus and cormels were prepared for glucomannan analysis. Glucomannan was quantified with the gravimetric method [13].

2.3. Data analysis

A correlation analysis be run between ten growth characters (X) and glucomannan (Y). Further, path analysis was conducted on the characters (X) that significantly correlate to glucomannan for each

location experiment, followed by model selection using the backward elimination method to determine the directly and indirectly affected yield (Y). The closeness of the relationship between variables X and Y was measured by Pearson's correlation and path analysis using Minitab 16 software.

Table 2. Local name and site origin of plant materials

No.	Local name	Site origin
1	Satoimo	Aceh Besar, Aceh
2	Keladi	Belitang, South Sumatra
3	Lahun Indung	Kuningan, West Java
4	Dempel	Mojokerto, East Java
5	Brentel	Sooko, Mojokerto, East Java
6	Talas Oshikawa	Kediri, East Java
7	Bentul	Kediri, East Java
8	Bentul	Malang, East Java
9	Talas Oshikawa	Lamongan, East Java
10	Salak	Karang Asem, Bali
11	Safira	Bantaeng, South Sulawesi
12	Satoimo	Bantaeng, South Sulawesi
13	Talas Jepang	Soppeng, South Sulawesi
14	Talas Jepang	Pinrang, South Sulawesi

3. Results

Pearson correlation analysis was performed on the trials for each experiment location since location and genotype significantly interacted with taro glucomannan. In the Setu, five characters had a negative significant correlation with glucomannan: leaf length, petiole length, sheath length, total petiole length, and plant height. In this location, the cormels number was the only character with a positive significant correlation to glucomannan. The characters with a significant positive correlation to glucomannan show similarity between; Cimanggu and Cijambe, i.e., cormus length, diameter of cormus, cormus weight, and cormel number (table 3).

Table 3. Pearson coefficient correlation between characters (X) and the glucomannan content (Y)

Characters	Pearson coefficient correlation with glucomannan content (Y)			
	Setu	Cimanggu	Cijambe	All location
Leaf length (X1)	-0.391 *	0.095	-0.174	0.185
Petiole length (X2)	-0.431 *	0.306	-0.305	0.144
Sheath length (X3)	-0.418 *	-0.022	-0.159	0.115
Total petiole length (X4)	-0.494 **	0.144	-0.314	0.103
Plant span (X5)	-0.373	0.091	-0.095	0.202
Plant height (X6)	-0.450 *	0.077	-0.234	0.134
Cormus length (X7)	-0.320	0.473 *	0.379 *	0.373 **
Diameter of cormus (X8)	-0.093	0.529 **	0.613 **	0.532 **
Cormus weight (X9)	-0.129	0.471 *	0.475 *	0.364 **
Cormels number (X10)	0.562 **	0.620 **	0.451 *	0.539 **

* = significant at 5%, ** = significant at 1%

The path analysis was executed for the characters with a significant correlation to glucomannan for each field and continued with the model selection with the backward elimination method. In Setu, the total petiole length and cormels number directly affect the glucomannan content (table 4). When a variable's direct effect coefficient on Y is low, it's important to consider the value of the effect of this

variable through another variable indirectly [14], and the chosen variables should have indirect effect coefficients higher than 0.09 [15]. The illustration in figure 1 explains that the positive direct effect found on the cormels number (X10, P = 0.483) and total petiole length (X4) has a negative direct effect (P = -0.398). In contrast, the indirect effects of X1, X2, X3, and X6 negatively contribute to glucomannan through the X4 variable.

Table 4. Path coefficient analysis of X1, X2, X3, X4, X6, and X10 with taro tuber glucomannan content in the Setu field experiment

Standardized characters	Direct effects	Indirect effect			Total effects
		X1	X2	X3	
Leaf length (X1)				-0.380	-0.404
Petiole length (X2)				-0.380	-0.448
Sheath length (X3)				-0.375	-0.421
Total petiole length (X4)	-0.398*			-0.096	-0.494
Plant height (X6)				-0.396	-0.468
Cormels number (X10)	0.483**			0.079	0.562
Total P	0.085				

* = significant at 5%, ** = significant at 1%

Figure 1. The cause-and-effect relationship diagram model for the Setu field experiment

The path analysis and backward elimination selection of experiment data in the Cimanggu field showed that the cormus length (X7, P = 0.318) and the cormels number (X10, P = 0.527) have a direct effect. The diameter (X8) and weight (X9) of the cormus have an indirect effect on glucomannan (table 5). The diagram of the cause-and-effect relationship model for the Cimanggu field experiment is illustrated in figure 2.

The analysis result of the data from the Cijambe field experiment displayed that the cormus diameter directly affected glucomannan (X7, P = 0.613) (table 6). The diameter of the cormus has a significant positive correlation to the cormus length (X7), corm weight (X9), and cormels number (X10), so all three characters have an indirect effect on glucomannan with a coefficient value >0.09 (figure 3).

The analysis result for data of all experiment location shows that cormus diameter (X8, P = 0.721), cormus weight (X9, P = -0.553) and cormels number ((X10, P = 0.385) have a direct effect on glucomannan, conversely cormus length (table 7). The diagram of the cause-and-effect relationship model for all field experiment is illustrated in figure 4.

Table 5. Path coefficient analysis of X7, X8, X9, and X10 with taro tuber glucomannan content in the Cimanggu field experiment

Standardized characters	Direct effects	Indirect effects				Total effects
		X7	X8	X9	X10	
Cormus length (X7)	0.318*				0.154	0.472
Cormus diameter (X8)		0.200			0.339	0.540
Cormus weight (X9)		0.213			0.328	0.541
Cormels number (X10)	0.527**	0.093				0.620
Total P	0.845					

* = significant at 5%, **= significant at 1%

Figure 2. The cause-and-effect relationship diagram model for the Cimanggu field experiment.

Table 6. Path coefficient analysis of X7, X8, X9, and X10 with taro tuber glucomannan content in the Cijambe field experiment

Standardized characters	Direct effects	Indirect effect				Total effects
		X7	X8	X9	X10	
Cormus length (X7)			0.215			0.215
Cormus diameter (X8)	0.613*					0.613
Cormus weight (X9)			0.508			0.508
Cormels number (X10)			0.388			0.388
Total P	0.613					

* = significant at 5%, **= significant at 1%

4. Discussion

Mannan is a polysaccharide and a representative of the hemicellulose group. It functions as plant storage and is deposited in the primary cell wall as galactomannan in the seed and glucomannan in the tuber. During embryonic growth and bud formation, this polysaccharide will be degraded and metabolized [16].

The direct and indirect positive effects on glucomannan content are mostly shown by the characters associated with the tuber (diameter, length, weight of cormus, and cormels number). In the Setu field, the higher glucomannan content is characterized by a higher cormels number and a smaller size of the petiole, sheath, and plant height. In the Cimanggu field, the high glucomannan content was identified by the high cormels number and the long size of the cormus. These two characteristics positively correlate with the diameter and weight of the cormus. The data from Cijambe informed that

glucomannan is defined by the large cormus size, the high weight of the cormus, and the high cormels number. The effects of the residual variable were 0.73 (Setu), 0.72 (Cimanggu), and 0.79 (Cijambe), which indicate that the model explained 27%, 28%, and 21% of the effect of X on Y, respectively. The residual showed lower value when the path analysis executed for entirety data (0.61) but the model clarifies only 39% of the X effect to Y.

Figure 3. The cause-and-effect relationship diagram model for the Cijambe field experiment

Table 7. Path coefficient analysis of X7, X8, X9, and X10 with taro tuber glucomannan for all field experiment

Standardized characters	Direct effects	Indirect effect				Total effects
		X7	X8	X9	X10	
Cormus length (X7)			0.563	-0.480	0.220	0.303
Cormus diameter (X8)	0.721**			-0.487	0.296	0.530
Cormus weight (X9)	-0.553**		0.635		0.281	0.363
Cormels number (X10)	0.385**		0.557	-0.403		0.539
Total P	0.553					

* = significant at 5%, **= significant at 1%

Figure 4. The cause-and-effect relationship diagram model for all field experiment

The cormels number showed a positive direct or indirect correlation with the taro tuber's glucomannan. Three factors must be met to establish an effective selection criterion: a high value of the direct effect coefficient, the association of correlation and path coefficients having a direct proportion, and a small difference (<0.05) between the value of correlation and the direct effect coefficient [17]. The association between the cormels number and glucomannan content satisfied two of the three requirements. The direct effect coefficient of the cormels number on the glucomannan content in this study was categorized as high [18], and there was a direct positive proportion value of the correlation coefficient and path coefficients of the cormels number on the glucomannan content. However, the last condition needs to be met since there was a higher than 0.05 difference between the correlation and direct effect coefficients. Additionally, the residual value, which was > 0.61 across all of experimental sites, made interpreting this model insufficient to explain more than 60% of the influence of anything other than the standardized independent variable. Therefore, the cormel number did not meet the selection criteria for determining the glucomannan content in the taro tubers.

5. Conclusion

The diameter, length, weight of the cormus, and number of the cormels all indicate a direct and indirect positive effect on taro tuber glucomannan content. In all trial sites, the character of the cormels number had a positive correlation with the glucomannan variable, either directly or indirectly, and a high value of the path coefficient. However, this trait only met some requirements as a selection criterion for taro tubers with high glucomannan content. It needs further research to determine an effective selection criterion for the taro breeding program.

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